

CSIS COMMENTARIES

CSIS Commentaries is a platform where policy researchers and analysts can present their timely analysis on various strategic issues of interest, from economics, domestic political to regional affairs. This commentaries serves as a medium for experts to disseminate knowledge and share perspectives in two languages – Bahasa Indonesia and English, enabling a diverse readership to engage with the content. Analyses presented in CSIS Commentaries represent the views of the author(s) and not the institutions they are affiliated with or CSIS Indonesia. Please contact the editorial team for any enquiries at publication@csis.or.id

CSIS Commentaries CSISCOM00325

March 20th, 2025

Refocusing the Purpose of Indonesia's CBDC

Adinova Fauri

Researcher, Department of Economics, CSIS Indonesia

adinova.fauri@csis.or.id

Bank of Indonesia (BI) is currently refining its efforts to issue a Central Bank Digital Currency (CBDC), known as the Digital Rupiah. This initiative reflects BI's commitment to integrating digital technology into the payment system. However, progress on issuing the Digital Rupiah appears to have stalled. Since introducing its roadmap, named *Project Garuda*, BI has yet to move beyond the proof-of-concept stage or conduct a pilot program.

The slow pace of development raises questions, especially considering that *Project Garuda* was launched in 2022, which was not included in Indonesia's *2019-2025 Payment System Blueprint*. The initiative originally emerged in response to BI's growing concerns over the rapid expansion of cryptocurrencies. Like many central banks worldwide, BI saw the rise of decentralized cryptocurrencies—operating outside the formal financial system—as a potential threat to monetary policy transmission and financial stability. The introduction of

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie grant agreement No 873119

the Digital Rupiah was expected to counterbalance the influence of cryptocurrencies and safeguard the financial system.

However, this sense of urgency has since diminished due to two key factors. First, BI has already prohibited the use of cryptocurrencies as a legal payment instrument in Indonesia, restricting their role to investment assets. As a result, cryptocurrencies no longer pose a direct threat to the country's monetary system. Second, the high volatility of crypto assets has reduced their appeal, confining demand primarily to high-risk investors.

Despite the reduced risk from cryptocurrencies, BI should not delay the issuance of the Digital Rupiah. Beyond countering crypto-driven instability, a CBDC offers broader economic benefits, particularly in enhancing cross-border transaction efficiency and deepening financial inclusion.

CBDCs and Cross-Border Transactions

One of the most promising applications of CBDCs is in cross-border transactions. While digitalization has improved domestic payment efficiency, cross-border transactions remain costly due to varying financial systems and regulatory frameworks, time zone differences, and also technological infrastructure gaps between countries.

By streamlining transaction processes, CBDCs could offer significant economic opportunities for Indonesia. In trade and tourism sectors, greater efficiency in cross-border payments could facilitate higher transaction volumes and boost revenue. However, the most tangible benefits would likely come from remittances. Lowering remittance costs per transaction could increase inflows and provide greater financial empowerment for recipient communities. To maximize these benefits, this CBDC agenda should be promoted within the framework of multilateral cooperation to establish international CBDC principles and standards, ensuring seamless cross-border interoperability.

CBDCs and Financial Inclusion

CBDCs also have the potential to deepen financial inclusion by reducing barriers to formal financial services. Digitalization has already played a key role in expanding financial access in Indonesia, with increased internet penetration driving the rise of e-wallets, digital banking, and fintech innovations. However, for a CBDC to meaningfully enhance financial inclusion, it must offer unique advantages beyond existing digital financial services.

One potential application is the integration of CBDCs into social transfer programs. By leveraging CBDCs for social assistance, the government could improve the efficiency of fund distribution, ensuring better targeting, timeliness, and accuracy. Additionally, incorporating CBDCs into social welfare schemes could encourage greater participation in the formal financial system, ultimately empowering underserved communities.

Challenges and Considerations

Despite its advantages, the implementation of a CBDC presents several challenges. The centralized infrastructure required for a Digital Rupiah must be secured against cyber threats, as public trust will be difficult to establish without robust security measures. Additionally, BI must navigate potential shifts in the global financial landscape, including issues of de-dollarization and exchange rate volatility. While reducing dependence on the U.S. dollar could enhance currency diversification, it also introduces financial risks, particularly if BI's foreign currency reserves increase substantially. To mitigate these risks, a thorough, risk-based assessment is essential to safeguard Indonesia's financial stability.

In summary, while the urgency behind launching the Digital Rupiah has waned, its potential to enhance cross-border transactions and financial inclusion remains significant. BI should refocus its efforts on realizing these broader benefits, ensuring that the Digital Rupiah becomes a key pillar of Indonesia's evolving financial ecosystem.

CSIS Indonesia, Pakarti Centre Building, Indonesia 10160

Tel: (62-21) 386 5532 | Fax: (6221) 384 7517 | csis.or.id

Please contact the editorial team for any enquiries at

publication@csis.or.id

